

Stealth and Bright Monomolecular Fluorescent Organic Nanoparticles Based on Folded Amphiphilic Polymer

Mayeul Collot, Jérémy Schild, Kyong T. Fam, Redouane Bouchaala, Andrey S. Klymchenko

Synthesis of amino BODIPYs

Amino-BODIPY 1 (BDP1) with different linkers

1 was synthesized according to a described procedure.¹

Azidopropylamine was synthesized according to a described procedure.²

NH₂-PEG-N₃ was obtained from Iris biotech (Germany).

Typical procedure for the synthesis of BDP1-N₃ BDP1-PEG₁₂-N₃. To a solution of **1** (1.300 g, 3.890 mmol, 1 eq) in DMF (35 mL) was added azidopropylamine (700 mg, 7.000 mmol, 1.8 eq), DIEA (1.5g, 11.67 mmol, 3 eq) and HATU (1.77 g, 4.670 mmol, 1.2 eq). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC (DCM/Acetone: 99/1) until completion. The solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (DCM/Acetone: 99/1) to obtain an orange solid (95%).

BDP1-N₃. Yield 95%. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃, MeOD₄) δ 5.98 (s, 2H, H-β), 3.28 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.23 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.92 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.43 (s, 6H, 2 CH₃), 2.33 (s, 6H, 2 CH₃), 1.87 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.70 (m, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, MeOD₄) δ 168.2 (CO), 150.1 (C Ar), 141.4 (C Ar), 136.6 (C Ar), 127.5 (C Ar).

117.8 (C Ar), 43.3 (CH₂), 33.2 (CH₂), 33.1 (CH₂), 32.0 (CH₂), 24.7 (CH₂), 23.4 (CH₂), 12.3 (CH₃), 10.4 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₂₀H₂₇BFN₆O [M-F]⁺ 397.2323, found 397.2313.

BDPI-PEG₁₂-N₃. Yield 77% ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.04 (s, 2H, H-β), 3.62 (m, 42H, 40H for PEG and 1 CH₂), 3.55 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.44 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.37 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.01 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.50 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.43 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.35 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.96 (m, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.1 (CO), 152.9 (C Ar), 144.7 (C Ar), 139.7 (C Ar), 130.5 (C Ar), 120.7 (C Ar), 70.7 (CH₂ PEG), 70.6 (CH₂ PEG), 70.6 (CH₂ PEG), 70.5 (CH₂ PEG), 70.5 (CH₂ PEG), 70.4 (CH₂ PEG), 70.4 (CH₂ PEG), 70.2 (CH₂ PEG), 70.0 (CH₂ PEG), 69.8 (CH₂ PEG), 50.7 (CH₂), 39.3 (CH₂), 36.2 (CH₂), 27.6 (CH₂), 27.5 (CH₂), 16.4 (CH₃), 14.4 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₄₁H₆₉BF₂N₆O₁₂Na [M+Na]⁺ 909.5034, found 909.4923.

Synthesis of BDPI-C₁₂. To a solution of **1** (300 mg, 0.898 mmol, 1 eq) in DMF (40 mL) was added 1,12-dodecylidiamine (539 mg, 2.695 mmol, 3 eq), DIEA (348mg, 2.695 mmol, 3 eq) and HATU (409mg, 1.078 mmol, 1.2eq). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. The reaction was monitored by TLC (DCM/MeOH/NEt₃ : 90/9/1) until completion. The DMF was removed under reduced pressure. The crude was purified by column chromatography on silica gel (DCM/MeOH/NEt₃ : 90/9/1) to obtain an orange solid with metallic reflect (**BDPI-C₁₂**, 21.9mg, 5%). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.04 (s, 2H, H-β), 3.23 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.43 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.00 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.67 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.50 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.41 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.30 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.95 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.48 (m, 4H, 2 CH₂), 1.25 (m, 16H, 8 CH₂). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.4 (CO), 154.0 (C Ar), 145.4 (C Ar), 140.5 (C Ar), 131.5 (C Ar), 121.7 (C Ar), 42.3 (CH₂), 39.7 (CH₂), 36.3 (CH₂), 33.8 (CH₂), 30.9 (CH₂), 29.6 (CH₂), 29.5 (CH₂), 29.5 (CH₂), 29.4 (CH₂), 29.4 (CH₂), 27.5 (CH₂), 27.4 (CH₂), 26.9 (CH₂), 26.8 (CH₂), 16.4 (CH₃), 14.4 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₂₉H₄₈BF₂NO [M+H]⁺ 516.3811, found 517.3897.

Typical procedure for Staudinger azide reduction. To a solution of **BDPI-N₃** (619 mg, 1.488 mmol, 1 eq), in THF (16 mL) with water (0.8 mL) was added PPh₃ (585 mg, 2.232 mmol, 1.5 eq). The solution was stirred overnight at 40°C. The reaction was monitored by TLC (DCM/MeOH/NEt₃: 90/9/1) until completion. The solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was purified by Flash chromatography on silica gel with solid deposit using Celite® (DCM/MeOH/NEt₃ : 90/9/1) to obtain an orange solid with metallic reflect (**BDPI**, 404 mg, 70%).

BDPI. Yield 70%, ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃ and Methanol-D₄) δ 6.00 (s, 2H, H-β), δ 3.15 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.91 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.61 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.38 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 2.34 (s, 6H, 2 CH₃), 2.28 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.84 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.58 (m, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃, MeOD₄) δ 173.5 (CO), 158.5 (C Ar), 145.6 (C Ar), 140.9 (C Ar), 131.3 (C Ar), 121.5 (C Ar), 38.2 (CH₂), 36.8 (CH₂), 35.8 (CH₂), 31.3 (CH₂), 27.7 (CH₂), 27.4 (CH₂), 15.6 (CH₃), 13.6 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₂₀H₂₉BF₂N₄O [M-F]⁺ 390.2402, found 390.2476.

BDPI-PEG₁₂. Yield 82%. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 6.03 (s, 2H, H-β), 3.61 (m, 42H, 40H for PEG and 1 CH₂), 3.50 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.43 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.99 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.86 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.49 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.41 (s, 3H, CH₃), 2.34 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.96 (m, 2H, CH₂). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.1 (CO), 152.9 (C Ar), 144.7 (C Ar), 139.7 (C Ar), 130.5 (C Ar), 120.7 (C Ar), 71.4 (CH₂ PEG), 69.4 (CH₂ PEG), 69.4 (CH₂ PEG), 69.2 (CH₂ PEG), 69.2 (CH₂ PEG), 69.1 (CH₂ PEG), 68.9 (CH₂ PEG), 49.5 (CH₂), 40.4 (CH₂), 38.3 (CH₂), 35.1 (CH₂), 26.6 (CH₂), 26.6 (CH₂), 15.3 (CH₃), 13.4 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₄₁H₇₀BF₂N₄NaO₁₂ [M+Na]⁺ 881.4954, found 881.4985.

Synthesis of Amino BODIPY with different bulkiness

Synthesis of BDP2

2 was synthesized according to a described procedure.³

Azidopropane-3-tosyle was synthesized according to a described procedure.⁴

BDP2-N₃. To a solution of **2** (400 mg, 1.080 mmol, 1 eq) in acetonitrile (10 mL) was added 1-azidopropane-3-tosyle (333 mg, 1.300 mmol, 1.2 eq), potassium carbonate (300 mg, 2.174 mmol, 2 eq) and potassium iodide (36 mg, 0.217 mmol, 0.2 eq). The reaction was stirred at room temperature and was monitored by TLC (Heptane/EtOAc: 7/3) until completion. The solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was purified by Flash chromatography on silica gel with solid deposit using Celite® (Heptane/EtOAc: 70/30) to obtain a yellow solid with metallic reflect (406 mg, 83%). The product was not pure according to NMR and was directly involved to the next step.

BDP2: See *Typical procedure for Staudinger azide reduction*. 60 mg, Yield 64%. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) 6.62 (s, 2H, CH Ar), 5.89 (s, 2H, H-β), 3.99 (t, 2H, CH₂), 2.88 (t, 2H, CH₂), 2.48 (s, 6H, 2 CH₃), 2.02 (s, 6H, 2 CH₃), 1.87 (m, 4H, 2 CH₂), 2.48 (s, 6H, 2 CH₃), 1.34 (s, 6H, 2 CH₃). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 159.2 (C Ar), 155.1 (C Ar), 142.3 (C Ar), 141.3 (C Ar), 136.7 (C Ar), 131 (C Ar), 126.6 (C Ar), 120.8 (C Ar), 114.1 (C Ar), 65.7 (CH₂), 39.1 (CH₂), 32.7 (CH₂), 19.8 (CH₂), 14.6 (CH₃), 13.5 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₂₄H₃₀BF₂N₃O [M+H]⁺ 426.2450, found 426.2526.

Synthesis of BDP3

3 was synthesized according to a described procedure.¹

BDP3-N₃. To a solution of **3** (500 mg, 1.282 mmol, 1 eq) in DMF (15 mL) was added azidopropylamine (231 mg, 2.308 mmol, 1.8 eq), DIEA (496 mg, 3.846 mmol, 3 eq) and HATU (585 mg, 1.538 mmol, 1.2 eq). The solution was stirred at room temperature for 1 hour. The reaction was monitored by TLC (DCM/Acetone: 99/1) until completion. The DMF was removed under pressure. (DCM/Acetone: 99/1) to obtain a red solid with metallic reflect (550 mg, 91%). ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.36 (m, 4H, 2CH₂), 3.06 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.49 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 2.40 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.36 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.34 (m, 8H, 4 CH₂), 1.97 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.80 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.04 (t, 6H, 2 CH₃). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 170.8 (CO), 151.4 (C Ar), 142.6 (C Ar), 134.8 (C Ar), 131.8 (C Ar), 130 (C Ar), 48.4 (CH₂), 36.3 (CH₂), 35.3 (CH₂), 27.8 (CH₂), 26.6 (CH₂), 26.4 (CH₂), 16.2 (CH₂), 13.8 (CH₃), 12.4 (CH₃), 11.4 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₂₄H₃₅BFN₆O [M-F]⁺ 453.2949, found 453.2936.

BDP3. See *Typical procedure for Staudinger azide reduction*. 242 mg, Yield 47%. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.34 (m, 2H, CH₂), 3.02 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.79 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.48 (s, 6H, 2CH₃), 2.39 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.37 (m, 2H, CH₂), 2.32 (m, 8H, 4 CH₂), 1.93 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.63 (m, 2H, CH₂), 1.02 (t, 6H, 2 CH₃). ¹³C-NMR (101 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 171.9 (CO), 152.3 (C Ar), 143.7 (C Ar), 135.8 (C Ar), 132.7 (C Ar), 131 (C Ar), 40 (CH₂), 38.1 (CH₂), 36.5 (CH₂), 31.8 (CH₂), 27.7 (CH₂), 27.5 (CH₂), 17.2 (CH₂), 14.8 (CH₃), 13.3 (CH₃), 12.4 (CH₃). HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd for C₂₄H₃₈BF₂N₄O [M+H]⁺ 447.3028, found 447.3109.

Synthesis of BDP4

BDP4-I: To a solution of **BDP1-N₃** (1.53 g, 3.680 mmol, 1 eq) in DCM (100 mL), was added N-Iodosuccinimide (1.82 g, 8.090 mmol, 2.2 eq). Quickly the solution went from orange to dark pink. The solution was allowed to stir overnight at room temperature. The reaction was monitored by TLC (DCM/Acetone: 99/1). The solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure. The obtained solid was insoluble in most organic solvents and was therefore filtered and washed with MeOH followed by DCM to obtain 2.03 g of a red solid. The TLC showed the full conversion of the starting material. The solid was involved in the next step with no further purification.

BDP4-N₃. To a suspension of **BDP4-I** (0.600 g, 0.898 mmol, 1 eq) in dioxane (100 mL) and water (10 mL) was added biphenyl-2-boronic acid (409 mg, 2.066 mmol, 2.3 eq), K₂CO₃ (371 mg, 2.694 mmol, 3 eq) and Pd(dppf)Cl₂ (0.650 mg, 0.090 mmol, 0.1 eq). The reaction was stirred overnight under reflux and was monitored by TLC (Heptane/EtOAc: 5/5). After a night 1 eq. of biphenyl-2-boronic acid (177mg) was added and the solution was stirred overnight at reflux to complete the reaction. The solvents were evaporated and the organic compound was washed with water and extracted with DCM (3 x 100 mL). The crude was purified by flash chromatography (Heptane/EtOAc: 5/5) to obtain a purple solid (270 mg, 42%). The product was obtained

as a clean mixture of 2 diastereoisomers. The purity was confirmed by LC-MS. HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd C₄₄H₄₃BF₂N₆NaO [M+Na]⁺ 743.3457, found 743.3453.

BDP4. To a solution of **BDP4-N₃** (150 mg, 0.208 mmol, 1 eq), in THF (2 mL) and water (0.1 mL) was added PPh₃ (82 mg, 0.312 mmol, 1.5 eq). The solution was stirred overnight at 40°C. The reaction was monitored by TLC (DCM/MeOH/NEt₃: 90/9/1) until completion. The solvents were evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was purified by Flash chromatography on silica gel with solid deposit using Celite® (DCM/MeOH/NEt₃: 90/9/1) to obtain a purple solid with metallic reflect (70 mg, 48%). The purity was confirmed by LC-MS. HRMS (ESI⁺), calcd C₄₄H₄₅BF₂N₄O [M+H]⁺ 694.3654, found 695.3727.

Synthesis of amphiphilic polymers from PMAO

General consideration

PMAO is sold with an average M_n of 30,000-50,000, which makes a polymer with ~100-140 repeating units per polymer molecule: M_n is the Molecular weight of the repeating unit A.

For the synthesis PMAO derivatives, calculation of the molar ratios of reactants was based on repeating monomer units A with a molecular weight of 350 g.mol⁻¹.

General procedures

Increasing amount of Jeffamine. In a 15 mL glass vial equipped with a magnetic bar and placed under an atmosphere of argon was added 20 mg of PMAO (0.057 mmol of repeating units). The polymer was dissolved in 3 mL of dry and degassed DMF under stirring. A volume of Jeffamine-1000 in its stock solution (DMF) was added according to the desired percentage of J-1000 (0 to 100 %). Then, 100 μL of DIEA (10 eq) were added to the solution. The solution was allowed to stir overnight at 60°C under argon and protected from light. The solution was transferred in a flask and the solvents were evaporated. The crude was dissolved in a DCM:Methanol solution (1:1) and was purified by size exclusion chromatography on LH-20 gel eluted with DCM:Methanol (1:1). The fractions were collected, the solvents were evaporated and the product was dried under high vacuum overnight. The obtained polymers were dissolved in dioxane at a concentration of 2 mg/mL and were formulated in milliQ water as described in the “materials and methods” section.

Fluorescent non-PEGylated, half PEGylated and fully PEGylated PMAO polymers

Non-PEGylated polymer. In a 15 mL glass vial equipped with a magnetic bar and placed under an atmosphere of argon was added 30 mg of PMAO (0.086 mmol of repeating units). The polymer was dissolved in 3 mL of dry and degassed DMF under stirring. BDP1 (0.05 eq) in its stock solution (10 mg/mL, DMF) was added. Then, 150 μL of DIEA (10 eq) were added to the solution. The solution was allowed to stir overnight at 60°C under argon and protected from light. The remaining anhydride functions were then hydrolysed by addition of 100 μL of water and the solution was allowed to stir 1 h at 60°C. The solution was transferred in a flask and the solvents were evaporated. The crude was dissolved in a DCM:Methanol solution (1:1) and was purified by size exclusion chromatography on LH-20 gel eluted with DCM:Methanol (1:1). The fractions were collected, the solvents were evaporated and the product was dried under high vacuum overnight. The obtained polymer was dissolved in dioxane at a concentration of 2 mg/mL and was formulated in milliQ water as described in the Materials and Methods section.

Half-PEGylated polymer. In a 15 mL glass vial equipped with a magnetic bar and placed under an atmosphere of argon was added 20 mg of PMAO (0.057 mmol of repeating units). The polymer was dissolved in 3 mL of dry and degassed DMF under stirring. BDP1 (0.05 eq) in its stock solution (10 mg/mL, DMF) was added, followed by DIEA (10 eq). Then J-1000 (1.2 eq, stock solution 200 mg/mL, DMF) was added. The solution was allowed to stir overnight at 60°C under argon and protected from light. The solution was transferred in a flask and the solvents were evaporated. The crude was dissolved in a DCM:Methanol solution (1:1) and was purified by size exclusion chromatography on LH-20 gel eluted with DCM:Methanol (1:1). The excess of J-1000 was eliminated and can be monitored by TLC. The fractions were collected, the solvents were evaporated and the product was dried under high vacuum overnight. The obtained polymer was dissolved in dioxane at a concentration of 2 mg/mL and was formulated in milliQ water as described in the Materials and Methods section.

Fully-PEGylated polymer. In a 15 mL glass vial equipped with a magnetic bar and placed under an atmosphere of argon was added 20 mg of PMAO (0.057 mmol of repeating units). The polymer was dissolved in 3 mL of dry and degassed DMF under stirring. BDP1 (0.05 eq) in its stock solution (10 mg/mL, DMF), followed by DIEA (10 eq). Then J-1000 (3 eq, stock solution 200 mg/mL, DMF) was added. Then, 100 µL of DIEA (10 eq) were added to the solution followed by 2 equivalents of HATU (added as a solid). The solution was allowed to stir at 60°C under argon and protected from light. The solution was transferred in a flask and the solvents were evaporated. The crude was dissolved in a DCM:Methanol solution (1:1) and was purified by size exclusion chromatography on LH-20 gel eluted with DCM:Methanol (1:1). The presence of impurities such as HATU derivatives and Jeffamine® were eliminated and can be monitored by TLC. The fractions were collected, the solvents were evaporated and the product was dried under high vacuum overnight. The obtained polymer was dissolved in dioxane at a concentration of 2 mg/mL and was formulated in milliQ water as described in the Materials and Methods section.

General procedure for increasing amount of fluorophore with full PEGylation. In a 15 mL glass vial equipped with a magnetic bar and placed under an atmosphere of argon was added 10 mg of PMAO (0.028 mmol of repeating units). The polymer was dissolved in 2 mL of dry and degassed DMF under stirring. Amino Bodipy in a stock solution (10 mg/mL, DMF) was added according to the desired percentage of fluorophore on the polymer (0 to 50 %). Then, 50 µL of DIEA (10 eq) were added to the solution. After 5 minutes, 3 equivalents of J-1000 were added from the stock solution (200 mg/mL, DMF) followed by 2 equivalents of HATU (added as a solid). The solution was allowed to stir overnight under argon and protected from light. The solution was transferred in a flask and the solvents were evaporated. The crude was dissolved in a DCM:Methanol solution (1:1) and was purified by size exclusion chromatography on LH-20 gel eluted with DCM:Methanol (1:1). The coloured fraction is the amphiphilic polymer. The presence of impurities such as HATU derivatives and Jeffamine® were eliminated and can be monitored by TLC. The fractions were collected, the solvents were evaporated and the product was dried under high vacuum overnight. The obtained polymer was dissolved in dioxane at a concentration of 2 mg/mL and was formulated in milliQ water as described in the Materials and Methods section.

Figure S1. NMR spectra of PMAO reacted with increasing amount of Jeffamine-1000 (400 MHz, CDCl_3). 0% Jeffamine is PMAO polymer with no modification.

Figure S2. Size of NPs obtained from polymers with increasing PEGylation rate. The sizes were assessed by DLS measurements of three independent formulations. For 0% PEG loading, non-modified PMAO was directly used.

Determination of PEGylation yield by $^1\text{H-NMR}$.

The first signal at 0.8-0.9 ppm, corresponding to the CH_3 of the aliphatic chain of PMAO, was integrated as 3 protons. The region from 2 to 5 ppm was then integrated as the signals of the CH_2O , CHN of Jeffamine-1000 (J-1000), in this region no PMAO signal is displayed (see control NMR of J-1000 and PMAO). J-1000 is sold as $\text{H}_2\text{N}-(\text{PO})_3-(\text{EO})_{19}-\text{OMe}$ (where PO is propylene glycol and EO is ethylene glycol) has 88 protons in the region 2 to 5 ppm. For the fully PEGylated polymer the baseline of the PMAO's CH_3 had to be corrected due to overlap with the CH_3 propyleneglycol group of J-1000. The PEGylation yield was calculated considering that 5% of the anhydride was used for introducing BODIPY and as the ratio of the integration value between 2 to 5 ppm region and the

theoretical value. The results gave a PEGylation yield of 96% for the half PEGylation of and a PEGylation yield of 88% for the full PEGylation.

$^1\text{H-NMR}$ of PMAO (left) and J-1000 (right) in CDCl_3 .

Figure S3. NMR spectra of fluorescent PMAO polymers reacted with increasing amount of Jeffamine-1000 (400 MHz, CDCl_3).

Figure S4. Absorption (A,B,E,F) and fluorescence (C,D,G,H) spectra of free BDP1-amino derivative (BDP1-NH₂) and fully PEGylated PMAO polymer with 5 mol% BDP1 in different solvents. Spectra (B,D,F,H) are normalized. Dye concentration was systematically 1 μ M. Excitation wavelength was 460 nm.

Figure S5. Cytotoxicity assay of NPs after 24 h incubation quantified by MTT assays. « 50% dye » corresponds to NPs with 50 mol% BDP4. 0.1% Triton X100 is a positive control.

Figure S6. Examples of FCS correlation curves (black) for fluorescein (50 nM) (A) and fully PEGylated NPs with 5 mol% of BDP1 (140 nM polymer) in water (B), PBS (C) and PBS with 10 μ M BSA (D), and corresponding fits (blue, 3D model with a triplet) using PyCorrFit software. For each condition, a single curve is shown out of 10 acquired in total.

Theoretical calculation for the size of a fully PEGylated monomolecular NP:

For this calculation we considered the higher molecular weight of PMAO (50,000 g.mol⁻¹) which corresponds to -140 repeating units per polymer chain (see above: general considerations).

The molecular weight of the fully PEGylated NP with 5% BODIPY is calculated as followed:

- Molecular weight of the average repeating unit (M_R):

$$M_R = M_D \times 0.05 + M_{PEG} \times 0.95 = 2301 \text{ g. mol}^{-1}$$

- Molecular weight of a single polymer molecule (M_P) is:

$$M_P = M_R \times \text{number of repeating units} = 2301 \times 140 = 322,210 \text{ g. mol}^{-1}$$

- The mass of a single polymer molecule (m_P) is:

$$m_P = 1/N_A \times M_P = 6,022 \times 10^{-23} \times 322,210 = 53,505 \times 10^{-19} \text{ g} = 5.35 \times 10^{-22} \text{ Kg}$$

Where N_A is the Avogadro number.

- The volume of the monomolecular NP (V_P) is calculated as follow considering a sphere composed of a matter with a density (d) equal to 1000 Kg/m³:

$$V_P = m_P / d = 5.35 \times 10^{-22} / 1000 = 5.35 \times 10^{-25} \text{ m}^3 = 535 \text{ nm}^3$$

- The radius of the NP (R) is:

$$R = (3V_P / 4\pi)^{1/3} = 5.03 \text{ nm}$$

- Diameter of the NP (D) is:

$$D = 2 \times R = 5.03 \times 2 = \underline{10.1 \text{ nm}}$$

Considering the lowest molecular weight (M_n) of PMAO indicated by the provider (30,000 g.mol⁻¹), the same calculation above yields a theoretical particle size of 8.5 nm.

Figure S7. Fluorescence spectra (A) and normalized spectra (B) of Nile Red (200 nM) at increasing concentration of BDP1 NPs (5 mol%). Concentration of polymer is used. (C,D) Corresponding changes in the fluorescence intensity at the maximum (C) and position of the maximum (D). Excitation wavelength was 540 nm.

Figure S8. Fluorescence spectra (A) and normalized spectra (B) of Nile Red (200 nM) at increasing concentration of Tween 80. (C,D) Corresponding changes in the fluorescence intensity at the maximum (C) and position of the maximum (D). Excitation wavelength was 540 nm.

Figure S9. Agarose gel (0.5 %) electrophoresis of NPs with 5 mol% BDP1 fluorophore displayed: at the interface (A) in the core (B) and in the PEG shell (C) (0.2 μg per well). D, E and F are the same in the presence of 5 μM BSA. The white arrow indicates the level of the wells. Scale bar is 0.5 cm.

Figure S10. Examples of FCS correlation curves (black) for fluorescein (50 nM) (A) and fully PEGylated NPs with 5 mol% of BDP4 (140 nM polymer) in water (B), PBS (C) and PBS with 10 μ M BSA (D), and corresponding fits (blue, 3D model with a triplet) using PyCorrFit software. For each condition, a single curve is shown out of ≥ 15 acquired in total.

Table S1. Physicochemical properties of the PMAO NPs with 5 mol% BDP4, obtained by FCS measurements.

Conditions	Size (nm) ^a	[Particles] (nm)	Number of polymer per NP ^b	Relative Brightness ^c
Water	16.8	98.2	1.42	4.06
PBS	18.4	78.2	1.79	4.10
10 μ M BSA in PBS	17.0	90.0	1.56	3.84

^a Obtained considering the reference (fluorescein) being 1 nm. ^b The polymer concentration was adjusted to 1 μ M fluorophore (corresponding to 140 nM polymer concentration). ^c Relative Brightness compared to the reference (fluorescein). The values were corrected according to the molar extinction coefficient values at the excitation wavelength (488 nm).

Figure S11. Histogram of intensity distribution of fully PEGylated PMAO NPs with 50 mol% of BDP4 and QDots-585 at the same measurement conditions using single-particle fluorescence microscopy (TIRF, λ_{Ex} = 532 nm, power density: 3 W cm⁻²). Integration time was 20×100 ms. 150 and 50 particles were analyzed for BDP4 NPs and QDots-585, respectively.

Figure S12. Comparison of the photostability of NPs at different BDP1 loading and FluoroSpheres™ (505/515). Irradiation wavelength was 486 nm.

Figure S13. Comparison of the photostability of NPs at different BDP4 loading and QDots-585. Irradiation wavelength was 486 nm.

Figure S14. Supplementary fluorescence images of co-injected NPs (green) and quantum dots QDot-655 (red) in three different cells (see Figure 8 caption for details).

NMR and mass spectra

^1H spectrum of **1**

^{13}C spectrum of **1**

¹H spectrum of BDP1-N₃

¹³C spectrum of BDP1-N₃

¹H spectrum of BDP1-PEG₁₂

¹³C spectrum of BDP1-PEG₁₂

¹H spectrum of BDP1-C₁₂

¹³C spectrum of BDP1-C₁₂

¹H spectrum of BDP2

¹³C spectrum of BDP2

^1H spectrum of **3**

^{13}C spectrum of **3**

¹H spectrum of BDP3-N₃

¹³C spectrum of BDP3-N₃

¹H spectrum of BDP3

¹³C spectrum of BDP3

¹H NMR spectrum of **BDP4** (400 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹³C spectrum of **BDP4**

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
314.17099		5315.5		
315.16754	1	22452.8		(M+H) ⁺
315.2194		1933.4		
316.17132	1	4069.6		(M+H) ⁺
334.17604		2450.1		
335.17304	1	9765.7	C17 H22 B F2 N2 O2	(M+H) ⁺
356.15847		3429.7		
357.15611	1	15465.2	C17 H21 B F2 N2 Na O2	(M+Na) ⁺
358.15959	1	2464.3	C17 H21 B F2 N2 Na O2	(M+Na) ⁺
691.32284	1	3498.1		

HRMS spectra of 1

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
396.23437		9763.2		
397.23133	1	45872		(M+H) ⁺
397.29162		3634		
398.23418	1	9905.3		(M+H) ⁺
438.22232		6777.5		
439.21953	1	31578.9	C20 H27 B F2 N6 Na O	(M+Na) ⁺
440.22212	1	6888.5	C20 H27 B F2 N6 Na O	(M+Na) ⁺
854.45191		5608.4		
855.44937	1	13879	C40 H54 B2 F4 N12 Na O2	(2M+Na) ⁺
856.45154	1	5600.8	C40 H54 B2 F4 N12 Na O2	(2M+Na) ⁺

HRMS spectra of BDP1-N₃

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
371.24071		9583.6	C20 H29 B F N4 O	(M+H) ⁺
390.2505		30767.2		
391.24759	1	150769.7	C20 H30 B F2 N4 O	(M+H) ⁺
392.25019	1	29952.8	C20 H30 B F2 N4 O	(M+H) ⁺
413.2292		9075.1	C20 H29 B F2 N4 Na O	(M+Na) ⁺

HRMS spectra of BDP1

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
420.2524	2	20809.3		
445.24639	2	48169		(M+2H) ²⁺
445.74769	2	21275.8		(M+2H) ²⁺
466.24078	2	34107.6	C41 H69 B F2 N6 Na2 O12	(M+2Na) ²⁺
887.50965	1	16089.9	C41 H70 B F2 N6 O12	(M+H) ⁺
904.53667	1	63556.5	C41 H73 B F2 N7 O12	(M+NH4) ⁺
905.53909	1	27103.1	C41 H73 B F2 N7 O12	(M+NH4) ⁺
908.49501		16633		
909.49234	1	86190.2	C41 H69 B F2 N6 Na O12	(M+Na) ⁺
910.49485	1	36291	C41 H69 B F2 N6 Na O12	(M+Na) ⁺

HRMS spectra of BDP1-PEG₁₂-N₃

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
248.69662		18217.2		
249.19532	2	83666.3		(M+2H)+2
249.69656	2	25591.5		(M+2H)+2
516.39222		42593.4		
517.38973	1	218730	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ B F ₂ N ₄ O	(M+H)+
518.39195	1	61892.9	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ B F ₂ N ₄ O	(M+H)+
539.37077		11704	C ₂₉ H ₄₇ B F ₂ N ₄ Na O	(M+Na)+

HRMS spectra of BDP1-PEG₁₂

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
425.25497		46387.9		
426.25262	1	235173.9	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ B F ₂ N ₃ O	(M+H)+
427.25509	1	55428.3	C ₂₄ H ₃₁ B F ₂ N ₃ O	(M+H)+

HRMS spectra of BDP2

Peak List

<i>m/z</i>	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
246.69682		18217.2		
249.19532	2	83666.3		(M+2H)+2
249.69656	2	25591.5		(M+2H)+2
516.39222		42593.4		
517.38973	1	218730	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ B F ₂ N ₄ O	(M+H)+
518.39195	1	61892.9	C ₂₉ H ₄₈ B F ₂ N ₄ O	(M+H)+
539.37077		11704	C ₂₉ H ₄₇ B F ₂ N ₄ Na O	(M+Na)+

HRMS spectra of BDP1-C₁₂

Peak List

<i>m/z</i>	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
370.2339		17459.1		
371.23168	1	78162.1		(M+H)+
372.23382	1	17140.2		(M+H)+
390.23557		7250.7		
391.2375	1	18481		
412.22245		11746.6	C ₂₁ H ₂₉ B F ₂ N ₂ Na O ₂	(M+Na)+
413.21927	1	49685.6		
414.22293	1	11864.6		
803.45021	1	14010.8		(2M+Na)+
804.45272	1	6359.7		

HRMS spectra of 3

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
452.29675		9115.7		
453.29361	1	43180.3		
453.35011		3399.5		
454.29656	1	10672.5		
494.28455		6281.2		
495.28169	1	29297	C24 H35 B F2 N6 Na O	(M+Na)+
496.28464	1	7699.5	C24 H35 B F2 N6 Na O	(M+Na)+
966.57632		5642.4	C48 H70 B2 F4 N12 Na O2	(2M+Na)+
967.57379	1	14338.1	C48 H70 B2 F4 N12 Na O2	(2M+Na)+
968.57579	1	7086.9	C48 H70 B2 F4 N12 Na O2	(2M+Na)+

HRMS spectra of BDP3-N₃

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
427.30384		11883.1		
446.31328		38322.8		
447.31097	1	193575.7	C24 H38 B F2 N4 O	(M+H)+
448.31305	1	45866.8	C24 H38 B F2 N4 O	(M+H)+
469.29179		10666	C24 H37 B F2 N4 Na O	(M+Na)+

A priori: Perte de HF

HRMS spectra of BDP3

Integration Peak List

Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	AreaSum%
7.78	8.01	8.36	182487	2903900	100	100

HPLC trace of BDP4-N₃ (ACN/Water, 0.1% formic acid)

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
701.35673	1	33386.4		(M+H)+
702.35906	1	15441		(M+H)+
742.3479	1	25421.9		
743.34537	1	140276.8	C44 H43 B F2 N6 Na O	(M+Na)+
744.34776	1	60491.3	C44 H43 B F2 N6 Na O	(M+Na)+
745.35045	1	13625.5	C44 H43 B F2 N6 Na O	(M+Na)+
759.3189	1	20273.9		(M+H)+
760.32155	1	9432.5		(M+H)+

Correspondrait à la perte d'un fluor du bon composé.

Bon composé si M+Na

Ou M+Na

LC-MS spectra of **BDP4-N₃**

Start	RT	End	Height	Area	Area %	AreaSum%
6.49	6.78	7.35	233883	4842263	100	100

HPLC trace of **BDP4** (ACN/Water, 0.1% formic acid)

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
694.37479	1	21260.1		
695.37273	1	112153.8	C44 H46 B F2 N4 O	(M+H)+
696.37513	1	48101.4	C44 H46 B F2 N4 O	(M+H)+
697.37765	1	10717.7	C44 H46 B F2 N4 O	(M+H)+
717.35413	1	24758.1	C44 H45 B F2 N4 Na O	(M+Na)+
718.35674	1	11038.1	C44 H45 B F2 N4 Na O	(M+Na)+

LC-MS spectra of **BDP4**